

Dynamic Resource Allocation on the Edge: A Causal and Contextually-Aware Machine Learning Approach

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Abstract. A new age of distributed and decentralized computing architectures has emerged in recent years due to the rise of edge computing. However, despite its potential, edge computing faces a variety of challenges, and one critical issue lies in the optimization of resource utilization due to the diverse nature of edge environments. Although resource allocation regards a topic heavily discussed in the area of edge computing, traditional approaches cannot manage to address efficiently this problem due to the heterogeneous nature of such environments. Motivated by this, in this paper, a novel dynamic resource allocation strategy for edge computing infrastructures is proposed, capable of identifying contextual information and causal relationships between the factors that affect an edge computing system and encapsulate them into the framework in order to perform informed adaptation decisions. The proposed framework is evaluated extensively in a simulated environment and the results show that it manages to optimize resource allocation and enhance the overall performance of the edge computing environment significantly when utilized.

Keywords: resource allocation, edge computing, machine learning, causal-aware ai, context-awareness

1 Introduction

In the recent years, the rise of edge computing has resulted in a new era of decentralized and distributed computing architectures. Edge computing, with its emphasis on processing data closer to the source, brings forth new opportunities for both consumers and businesses. From managing Internet of Things (IoT) devices for transportation [23], [7], to smart cities [6], [8], [9], edge computing has proven to be the most effective solution.

Yet the challenges that still remain are plenty. One of the key challenges which needs to be addressed, regards in the efficient utilization of resources [21], [14] and the demand for real-time and context-aware applications [16] at the edge intensifies, the need for a robust dynamic resource allocation framework becomes increasingly important.

Traditional resource allocation strategies frequently fall short in addressing the complexity of edge computing environments, which are characterized by a variety of devices, varying workloads, and dynamic contextual factors [18]. For this reason, in this paper, a novel dynamic resource allocation framework is proposed. The proposed framework is designed to perform dynamic resource adaptations on the nodes of an edge computing infrastructure, such as the one shown in Figure 1. The designed framework performs predictions with a Machine Learning (ML) model, trained with a causally and contextually enhanced dataset which encompasses this information and allows the model to better generalize and adapt better to dynamic environments as an edge computing network.

The remainder of this paper is constructed as follows: Section 2 provides a detailed analysis of the State-of-the-Art with respect to dynamic resource allocation and adaptation on the edge. Section 3 presents the problem formulation and describes the proposed dynamic resource allocation framework overview. Section 4 describes the evaluation in which the proposed framework was put under. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper, and discusses future works based on the current research.

2 Related Work

Dynamic resource allocation refers to the process of adapting the computing resources of a system based on the workload or demand. It is a research topic related to cloud computing [20], yet with the emergence of edge computing a major shift towards the research of resource allocation at the edge was acknowledged.

To start with, Tang *et al.* [17] proposed a resource allocation strategy for latency-critical application in hybrid cloud and edge computing infrastructures. The proposed strategy is comprised of two algorithms, the resource scheduling algorithm and the resource matching algorithm. The first one, calculates the cost of scheduling tasks given the transmission cost between the data centers (*i.e.*, the cloud infrastructure part) and the edge servers. Taking into account the outcomes of the resource scheduling algorithm, the resource matching algorithm optimizes the resources to be allocated for the given task on an edge server, taking into consideration the task priorities, the overall network transmission cost and the resource location.

The authors of [3], proposed a computation and communication resources optimization for Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) environments towards the optimization of throughput using a dynamic throughput maximum (DTM) algorithm based on the Lyapunov optimization. In a similar manner, in [11] the authors proposed a resource allocation strategy for Virtual Machines (VM) in MEC, taking into consideration the users' mobility [13]. Furthermore, the algorithm identifies the optimal path between the users and the deployed VM taking into consideration their movement.

Based on the work found in [5] and [22], Gong *et al.* [4] proposed a Generative Adversarial Network (GAN)-assisted dynamic resource allocation scheme for MEC, in which they analyze the historical data set related to the users'

mobility to predict the demand for each edge node in the next time slot and perform allocation decisions according to this information information.

3 Dynamic Resource Allocation Framework

Fig. 1: The Hybrid Cloud / Edge architecture of the system.

3.1 Problem Formulation

Consider an edge network as the one depicted in Figure 1. The edge network can be represented as a graph G , where $G = (V, E)$, $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_m\}$ are the

edge nodes and $E = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\}$ are the edges of the network connecting the nodes. The goal of the proposed resource allocation framework is twofold: (i) to predict the resource utilization for the nodes of the given edge network, (ii) dynamically adapt the resources of any given node depending on the predictions.

For each node $v_i \in V$, $c_i = c(v_i)$ represents its storage capacity, $m_i = m(v_i)$ represents its memory usage, and $p_i = p(v_i)$ its CPU usage at any given time. Furthermore, for each node, $l_{ij} = l(v_i, v_j)$ contains the calculated least distance between i -th and j -th nodes. Thus, a list of all least distances for any node i is found in the $L = \{l_{ij}\}$ distance matrix. The distance in this case refers to the physical distance (*i.e.*, the number of edges that connect the two servers). In addition, the service migration cost w_{ij} between nodes i and j is measured.

Furthermore, the transmission delay between any two nodes i and j (where j maybe the actual user in the network) is defined as:

$$t_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^n \delta + T_{proc} + T_{trans} \quad (1)$$

where δ is the default delay of the edge that connects i and j in ms, T_{proc} the processing time of the service and T_{trans} the transmission delay between i and j which is equal to $\frac{d_k}{b_{ij}}$, where d_k is the size of the transmitted data and b_{ij} the available bandwidth for the edge i and j .

Thus, the overall delay can be defined as the sum of all pairs t_{ij} for any i and j :

$$T = \sum_{i=1, j=1}^m t_{ij} \quad (2)$$

Given the above, the proposed framework needs to perform actions in order to optimize resource utilization of the overall edge network, while reducing the overall delay.

3.2 Dynamic Resource Allocation framework's Components

The proposed Dynamic Resource Allocation framework is comprised of the following components, as also depicted in Figure 3: (i) the Monitoring component, (ii) the Resource Usage Prediction component, (iii) the Intervention Model Generation component, and (iv) the Resources Adaptation component, which will all be further explained below.

Monitoring component This component is used for monitoring the resources of all nodes in the edge network. It is in essence a system which monitors the edge nodes and keeps track of key metrics including CPU, and memory utilization, available disk storage, along with network metrics such as egress and ingress bandwidth, and latency. All metrics are then stored in a MySQL database.

Fig. 2: The produced Causal Diagram which was utilized for the generation of the causal features.

Resource Usage Prediction component This component is used for the prediction of the resource usage of any edge node at a given time. It utilizes a novel *data enhancement method*, as explained below, in order to predict the utilization of two key metrics; CPU and memory.

First, it is important to discuss how the data is enhanced. In more detail, there are two methods used for the enhancement of the dataset. The first regards causal feature generation [13], while the second regards the identification of the most important instances in the dataset and the generation of the new enhanced dataset [15].

Starting with the *causal features* generation, as also shown in Algorithm 1, the process starts with the identification of the causal relationships among the features of the dataset. This is performed using the Direct Linear non-Gaussian structural equation model (DirectLiNGAM) [12]. The outcome of DirectLiNGAM can be represented as an acyclic causal graph which each node represents a feature of the dataset and the edges represent a causal relationship between two features, as shown in Figure 2, such that if A and B are features of the dataset, then $A \xrightarrow{x} B$ means that A is a cause of B , while the number x on the arrow represents the causal influence of A on B . Subsequently, for any target (*i.e.*, in this case CPU usage and memory usage) the parents (*i.e.*, the causes of those features) are selected. For each identified tuple of a target variable and its parent, and for each instance in the dataset, the number of instances that have the same value as the target variable, multiplied by the z-score ($z_i = \frac{e_i - \mu}{\sigma}$)

of the effect e_i of its cause is calculated, as shown in Algorithm 1 (line 11). This represents the new causal feature which is then appended to the original dataset. The above procedure is repeated for every identified target feature or cause feature.

Fig. 3: High-level overview of the Dynamic Resource Allocation platform.

Next, the identification of the influential instances and the generation of the *contextually enhanced dataset* takes place, as depicted in Algorithm 2. First, the ML algorithm is trained using the original dataset and the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) are calculated. Afterwards, the instances of the dataset are evaluated with respect to their influence as follows. The instance is removed from the original dataset, the model is retrained and the two metrics are recalculated. If the model's performance is worse (*i.e.*, the RMSE and MAE are increased) this instance is considered influential, and it is appended to the influential instances dataset (\mathcal{I}). Upon measuring its importance, the instance is inserted back into the original dataset. Once the above procedure is over, the remaining instances that were not initially considered influential are evaluated again by measuring the distance they have from any of the already-identified influential instances. If this distance (measured in degrees since they are represented as a vector of an X -dimensional space, where X is the number

Algorithm 1 Causal Features generation.

```

1:  $dLiNGAM \leftarrow \text{DirectLINGAM}(\mathcal{D})$ 
2:  $pc \leftarrow \mathbf{p\_c}(dLiNGAM)$  if causal effect value  $e_i$  is positive
3: for each tuple in  $pc$  do
4:   calculate occurrences of an instance appears in the dataset for  $P(t|CF_i)$ 
5: end for
6: for each tuple  $i$  in  $pc$  do
7:    $max((P(t|CF_i)) \leftarrow$  calculate max occurrences in the dataset for  $P(t|CF_i)$  for
   any tuple in  $pc$ 
8:    $min(P(t|CF_i)) \leftarrow$  calculate min occurrences in the dataset for  $P(t|CF_i)$  for any
   tuple in  $pc$ 
9: end for
10: for each tuple  $i$  in  $pc$  do
11:    $causalFeature_i \leftarrow \frac{P(t|CF_i) - min(P(t|CF_i))}{max(P(t|CF_i)) - min(P(t|CF_i))} \times z_i$   $\setminus \setminus z_i$  is the z-score of the
   effect  $e_i$ 
12:    $\mathcal{D} : \mathcal{D} \cup causalFeature_i$  // Append the new causal feature to the existing
   dataset
13: end for
14: return  $\mathcal{D}$ 

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of the features) is less than a given value Θ , the instance is considered influential as well and appended to the \mathcal{I} dataset.

The above procedure only happens once, or every time the selected ML model is retrained. The process starts with selecting the monitoring information of a node from the monitoring data collected and stored in the MySQL database. Once the contextually enhanced dataset is generated, the ML model needs to be trained in order to forecast the CPU and memory utilization of a given edge node, given the collected historical data. Random Forest Regressor was selected with 1000 trees, since it has been proven efficient in such tasks [1].

Intervention Model Generation component This component is responsible for making the decisions with respect to the actions that need to be undertaken. Given the end goal, which is to reduce the overall latency of the network, and optimize resource usage, the Intervention Model Generation component has a set of options, taking into consideration the predictions made by the Resource Usage Prediction component.

The goal is to reduce the average delay of the system and keep it under a given threshold, which in this case is set to 10 ms. If the average delay stays beneath this value, but the CPU and / or memory utilization is over 80% no changes are required to be made, while if the CPU or the memory utilization is below the 80% threshold the Intervention component requests freeing resources (scaling down) of those (edge) nodes with the least CPU and memory utilization in order to free unused resources. On the other hand, if the average delay exceeds the 10 ms threshold, it requests deploying the service .

Algorithm 2 Context identification and dataset enhancement.

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1:  $\text{fit}(\mathcal{D})$ 
2:  $\mathcal{I} = []$ 
3: calculate  $MAE(\mathcal{D})$ 
4: calculate  $RMSE(\mathcal{D})$ 
5: for  $i \in \mathcal{D}$  do
6:    $\mathcal{D}^{-i} : i \notin \mathcal{D}$ 
7:    $\text{fit}(\mathcal{D}^{-i})$ 
8:   calculate  $MAE(\mathcal{D}^{-i})$  and  $RMSE(\mathcal{D}^{-i})$ 
9:   if  $RMSE(\mathcal{D}^{-i}) \geq RMSE(\mathcal{D})$  &&  $MAE(\mathcal{D}^{-i}) \geq MAE(\mathcal{D})$  then
10:      $\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{I} \cup i$ 
11:      $\mathcal{D} : \mathcal{D} - i$ 
12:   end if
13: end for
14: for  $i : i \in \mathcal{D} \wedge i \notin \mathcal{I}$  and  $k : k \in \mathcal{I}$  do
15:   if  $\theta(i, k) \leq \Theta$  and  $i \neq k$  then
16:      $\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{I} \cup i$ 
17:   end if
18: end for
19: return  $\mathcal{I}$ 

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Resource Adaptation component This component is responsible for performing the necessary adaptations to the edge infrastructure as indicated by the Intervention component. In more detail, in the first case where scaling down is requested, the Resources Adaptation component, based also on the real-time monitoring information coming from the Monitoring component, identifies the nodes with the least CPU and / or memory utilization and requests a downscale. In the second case, the Resources Adaptation component, starts with scaling up on the nodes with the highest resource utilization. If this adaptation is sufficient and the average delay meets the 10 ms threshold, no other changes are required. Alternatively, if this change does not succeed to reduce the average latency (after a given number of iterations), the Resource Adaptation component identifies the nodes with the highest utilization and those with the least utilization and performs a service migration in order to utilize those nodes more efficiently, given that their current CPU and memory utilization along with their available storage capacity allows the services to be deployed there.

4 Performance Evaluation

In order to evaluate the proposed resource allocation framework different simulations were executed in an edge computing network as described below. The network topology regards a randomly generated network graph G , with 50 edge servers. 100 services were initially deployed randomly and were set to require 5 – 10% of CPU, 10 – 15% of memory and 1 – 5% of storage. When they were first deployed, they were assigned 10–15% of the server’s available CPU, 15–20%

of memory, and 5 – 10% storage capacity. The edges of the graph represented the delay which was randomly set in the range of 6 – 20 ms. 1000 users were gradually introduced into the edge network and the latency between the users and the node to which they were connected was also randomly set from 6 to 20 ms. The different kinds of services can be categorized as CPU- or memory-intensive and various simulations were executed. For instance, when it comes to CPU-intensive applications, every 10 users required an additional 5% CPU on the service they were using.

Fig. 4: Comparison of average CPU utilization for the entire edge network.

In order to assess the proposed resource allocation framework, the following metrics were used: the average latency, CPU and memory utilization for the overall edge network, and 3 metrics related to the performance of the Resource Usage Prediction component. Given that in both cases for the CPU and memory utilization this was a time-series forecasting (regression) task, the utilized metrics that were used are Mean Squared Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and the R2-score.

To start with the overall performance of the proposed framework, the results show that the overall latency was improved when compared to the edge network when the resource adaptation was not utilized. As depicted in Figures 4, 5, and 6, the results show that the proposed approach managed to significantly reduce the average utilization of the network’s computing resources, while reducing the average latency.

Fig. 5: Comparison of average Memory utilization for the entire edge network.

Fig. 6: Comparison of average latency for the entire edge network.

Fig. 7: CPU utilization prediction using the original dataset.

Fig. 8: CPU utilization prediction using the influence-based, causally enhanced dataset.

In more detail, with the utilization of CPU was on average reduced by approximately 7%, while the average memory utilization was decreased by approximately 8.1%. Similar results can be extracted when looking at the average latency for each one of the 100 services deployed of the edge network in Figure 9. To summarize, the overall latency of the edge network was 17.64 ms when the proposed framework was not utilized, while it was equal to 16.4 ms when the framework was utilized, resulting in a $\sim 8.1\%$ improvement.

The second part of the evaluation was related to the assessment of the Resource Usage Prediction component’s performance. The dataset was composed of monitoring data related to the CPU, memory and disk utilization, along with networking metrics such as latency, egress bandwidth, ingress bandwidth, etc. The dataset had a total of 1,260,431 rows. 90% was used for training while the remaining 10% was used for testing. Initially, the ML model (the Random Forest Regressor) was trained using the original resource utilization data without being enhanced using the causal feature generation and the influence-based instances selection methods. Next, the training was performed again, with the difference that the two methods were now utilized and the results show a significant improvement, as also depicted in Figures 7 and 8 with the performance of the model being improved when trained on the enhanced dataset which was also decreased in size since only the influential instances were finally used (the enhanced dataset was comprised of 1,031,431 instances, *i.e.*, an $\sim 18\%$ decrease in size).

The results on the test set show that initially the MSE was equal to 109.374 while in the case of the model being trained with the enhanced dataset the MSE was equal to 48.476 which indicates that the model’s predictions were closer to the actual values on average, when trained with the enhanced dataset. Similar results are also derived from the MAE, were it was initially measured 8.084 while in the enhanced dataset training the MAE was equal to 6.024 which lead to the conclusion that the absolute differences between predicted and actual values were closer when trained to the enhanced dataset. The R2-score when the original dataset was used was equal to 0.631 while it was equal to 0.798 when the enhanced dataset was used instead which meaning a better fit of the model on the enhanced dataset. Similar results were also observed for the memory usage prediction.

5 Conclusions

This work presented a dynamic resource allocation framework for edge computing using a causal, contextually enhanced ML approach. The proposed framework identifies an edge network in the form of a graph, and the overall goal is to optimize the Quality of Service (QoS) for the network’s users, which translates to reduced overall latency. In order to achieve that, a ML-based solution is implemented which predicts the resource usage of the edge nodes in the network, and based on those predictions, certain actions need to be taken. The proposed framework was evaluated in a simulation scenario where 50 edge nodes

Fig. 9: Average latency of the 100 services when the resource allocation framework is used and is not used.

were introduced in an edge network with 1000 users. The simulations suggested a significant improvement when the proposed framework is utilized in terms of latency (on average 8.1%). Furthermore, the utilization of the data enhancement method has boosted the performance of the ML model, leading to an increase of $\sim 26.5\%$ for the R2 score and a decrease of the MAE by $\sim 25\%$. It is within our next steps to further work on the advancement of the Resources Adaptation component and consider other more robust solutions, such as the utilization of Reinforcement Learning (RL) methods [19, 2, 10], which should improve the current framework and allow it to learn optimal resource allocation strategies in such dynamic and diverse environments as an edge computing network.

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